

Table 1. Means for the variables studied and total rainfall for each rice line during the 1987 cropping season at Morogoro, Tanzania.^a

Cultivar	Total rainfall (mm)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Mean panicle length (cm)	Tillers/plant (no.)	Harvest index (%)	Filled grains/panicle (%)	Drought effect score (0-7)
Farox 229	297.4	140.0 abc	0.9 bc	73.0 cd	15.1 d	5.0 b	26.0 ab	44.0 b	1.8 b
IRAT104	297.1	135.0 d	1.8 a	78.3 bc	17.8 ab	6.0 ab	46.0 a	65.0 ab	1.7 b
IRAT156	297.4	139.3 bc	0.8 bc	76.0 bcd	18.4 ab	6.0 ab	48.0 a	89.0 a	1.7 b
IRAT161	297.1	129.3 e	1.3 b	78.3 bc	16.8 bcd	8.0 a	31.0 ab	63.0 ab	2.0 b
IRAT170	293.8	126.7 f	0.4 cd	66.3 de	15.7 cd	7.0 ab	31.0 ab	50.0 ab	2.7 a
ISA6	297.4	138.7 c	0.9 bc	70.0 cd	19.3 a	6.7 ab	31.0 ab	60.0 ab	2.0 b
ITA128	297.1	135.0 d	0.8 bc	68.0 cde	17.2 bc	7.3 ab	26.0 ab	51.0 ab	2.2 ab
ITA235	293.8	124.0 f	0.7 bc	76.0 bcd	18.6 ab	8.0 a	28.0 ab	56.0 ab	1.8 b
ITA305	298.3	125.3 f	0.8 bc	58.0 e	15.5 cd	6.7 ab	43.0 ab	53.0 ab	2.2 ab
ITA315	293.8	122.3 g	0.4 cd	68.3 cde	16.9 bcd	8.3 a	17.0 b	51.0 ab	1.8 b
OS6	297.1	138.0 c	0.3 d	84.7 ab	16.7 bcd	5.3 b	26.0 ab	46.0 ab	2.4 ab
Supa	297.8	146.7 a	0.4 cd	93.3 a	18.6 ab	7.0 ab	19.0 b	41.0 b	2.7 a
\bar{X}		133.4	0.80	74.2	17.2	6.8	31.0	56.0	2.1
SX		0.7	0.18	3.4	0.6	0.7	8.0	7.3	0.2
CV (%)		0.9	38.5	7.7	6.1	17.9	17.7	23.2	16.8

^aIn a column, mean values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) by DMRT.

Table 2. Simple correlation coefficients between the variables studied in the upland rice lines at Morogoto, Tanzania, 1987 season.^a

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1. Drought effect	—											
2. Days to maturity	-0.127	—										
3. Plant height	0.176	0.612*	—									
4. Panicle length	-0.169	0.514	0.451	—								
5. Tillers/plant	0.067	0.444	-0.169	0.253	—							
6. Panicle weight	-0.570*	-0.029	0.039	0.261	0.095	—						
7. Filled grains/panicle (%)	-0.637	-0.024	-0.152	0.407	0.123	0.872**	—					
8. Harvest index	-0.406	0.015	-0.274	0.036	-0.352	0.669*	0.745**	—				
9. Panicles/m ²	0.238	-0.498	-0.273	0.235	0.629*	-0.111	0.036	-0.277	—			
10. 1000-grain weight	0.243	-0.192	-0.173	-0.703*	-0.371	-0.274	-0.359	-0.075	-0.198	—		
11. Plants/m ²	0.228	-0.280	-0.373	0.301	0.604*	0.088	0.233	0.004	0.722**	-0.139	—	
12. Grain yield	-0.608*	0.099	-0.029	-0.125	0.097	0.808**	0.672*	0.599*	-0.163	0.126	0.131	—
Significance of regression on yield ^b	(-ve)*					(+ve)*		(+ve)*				

^a*, ** denote significance at $P < 0.05$ and 0.01 , respectively. ^bMultiple regression when all the variables were included in the equation.

Supa. The low yields were attributed to drought, particularly during the reproductive stage, between booting and grain filling. After two rainless weeks

then, we provided two supplemental furrow irrigations a week.

Panicle weight and harvest index had positive effects on seed yield (Table 2).

Panicle weight, filled grains/panicle, harvest index, and yield were positively associated. □

Yield potential of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V at Ndop Plain, Northwest Cameroon

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Rice, a relatively new crop in Cameroon, is grown on about 20,000 ha

of irrigated lands. Ndop Plain at an altitude of 1,200 m above sea level in the Northwest Province is one of the three major rice production areas. The primary constraints to increased productivity are low temperature and associated severity of sheath rot (ShR) and grain discoloration (GID).

Tainan V, a popular traditional variety, has bold, short, chalky grains and poor keeping quality. IR7167-33-2-3 was released for general cultivation in

1987. It has medium-long, less chalky grains, and fair keeping quality. It yields higher than Tainan V, is low temperature tolerant, and resistant to ShR and GID. It is also 8 d shorter in duration.

We examined the yield potential of the two varieties over several seasons from on-station and farmers' field trials. The on-station yield trials used early transplanting at 25- × 20-cm spacing, 2-3 seedlings/hill, and 60-40-40 kg

Table 1. Performance of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V in research station observational yield trials. Cameroon, 1987 and 1988.

Variety or line	Grain yield ^a		Duration (d)	Reaction ^b to		Panicle exertion ^b
	(t/ha)			Sheath rot	Grain discoloration	
	1987	1988				
Tainan V	4.3	3.3	150	5	5	3
IR7167-33-2-3	5.5	4.4	142	3	3	3

^aMean of 6 trials/year. ^bStandard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale.

NPK/ha. The farmers' field trials were conducted according to normal farmer practices.

IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan V in 1987 and 1988 trials at the Bamunka research site (Table 1). In 1988 on-

station trials, IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan V by an average 36%. IR7167-33-2-3 also showed greater resistance to ShR and GID.

In farmers' fields in the Bamunka area, IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan

Table 2. Yields of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V in farmers' fields at Ndop Plain, Cameroon.

Variety or line	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	
	1987	1988
Tainan V	3.4	3.2
IR7167-33-2-3	4.9	4.5

^aMean of 6 farms sampled/year.

V on all six farms sampled in 1987 (Table 2). Yield trends were similar in 1988.

IR7167-33-2-3 has an average yield advantage over Tainan V of 32% on station and 45% in farmers' fields. □

ASD17, a short-duration red rice variety for tail end irrigation areas of Tambiraparani Delta and Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu

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Short-duration red rice culture AS688, isolated from the double cross derivative of ADT31/Ratna//ASD8/IR8, has been released as rice variety ASD17 for

cultivation in tail end irrigation areas of Tambiraparani tract and Kanyakumari District. It is suitable for cultivation during kannipoo season (Apr-Jul) in Kanyakumari and kar season (Jun-Sep) and late pishanam season (Nov-Feb) in Nellai Kattabomman District. ASD17 can replace local varieties Kuruvai, Arupatham kuruvai, and Annapoorna in Kanyakumari and Thuyamalli in Nellai Kattabomman.

ASD17 is 96 cm tall and matures in 100 d. Mean grain yield was 5.4 t/ha over 10 yr in 27 different trials (see table). Mean straw yield was 9.0 t/ha.

Early senescence is its distinguishing character. The variety produces its maximum grain yield when younger

seedlings (18-20 d) are transplanted. Grain is short and bold red rice, with high consumer preference.

ASD17 has field tolerance for tungro and blast and moderate resistance to brown planthopper and sheath rot. □

Performance of some improved rice varieties under irrigated and rainfed lowland conditions at Parwanipur, Nepal

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We studied yield and yield attributes and some agronomic traits of 10 released and 1 prerelease variety under irrigated and rainfed lowland conditions in 1988 wet season (May-Oct).

The experiments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Seeds were sown on dry seedbed on 26 May for irrigated rice and 7 Jun for rainfed lowland. Seedlings were transplanted at 1 seedling/hill, 25 × 25cm row spacing, 30 d after sowing. Fertilizer was applied at 80-20-20 kg NPK/ha. Plots were protected against weeds, insect pests, and diseases. Net area harvested was 5.0 m²/plot.

Filled grains were separated from unfilled grains using Dockaging

Performance of ASD17 in Tamil Nadu.

Trial	Trials (no.)	% increase				
		TKM9	ASD8	Cauvery	Arupatham kuruvai	Anna-poorna
Rice Research Station, Ambasamudram, 1979-88	27	6.8	—	—	—	—
Adaptive Research Trials, Kanyakumari District, 1981 wet season	10	2.6	—	—	—	—
1981 semidry season	7	6.1	—	—	—	—
1984 and 1987	15	—	—	—	1.8	—
1988	20	—	—	—	—	7.4
Adaptive Research Trials, Tirunelveli District, 1987 and 1988	34	—	37.3	—	—	—
All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, 1981 direct seeded rainfed	9	—	—	7.7	—	—
All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, 1981 direct seeded irrigated	2	—	—	1.7	—	—
All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, 1981 transplanted	9	—	—	10.1	—	—